

Web Audio and ESP32, Sound art and tangible real-time interaction via network, “Music for Elements” ecology and intermediality

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a research and creation project entitled “Music for Elements”, a connected sound itinerary whose ecological issues question the practice of intermedia sound art and IoT technologies as a means of reconciling city dwellers with the city and ecology. Inspired by biomimicry and DIY design, the idea is to implement a web audio application on an ESP32 microcontroller configured as a Wi-Fi access server, in order to sonify data from an urban ecosystem in real time via a WebSocket server. Light intensity, water movement, water level and temperature, ambient noise level, air temperature and quality, soil moisture and wind strength are all environmental factors that measure the ecological impact of humans on their environment and highlight the presence of life in urban areas. In a sensitive approach, the data collected by these devices represent information and variables that can influence the creative process of a sound work, as real-time composition parameters. These processes of technological interaction within an artistic device would make it possible to recreate the link between humans and living beings. The project is presented as a prototype and is currently under development. Initial experiments have yielded convincing results thanks to the use of biomimicry process and WebSocket technology for real-time sound interaction with the environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

We present a research and creation project that involved the realization of a technical device capable of managing tangible interaction processes, communicating over a local network in real time and producing synthesized sounds through a mobile interface, while being adapted to the conditions of an external environment. IoT technology makes it possible to use embedded systems, microcontrollers and sensors to probe the environment,

gathering data specific to the presence of ecosystems. They also enable the creation of a WebSocket communication server and the implementation of a Web Audio application to generate real-time sound compositions using environmental data, providing an artistic interpretation of ecosystems in urban green areas. This project is still in its early stages.

2. SCIENTIFIC AND ARTISTIC ISSUES

“Music For Elements” is a connected sound itinerary, the aim of which is to bring natural and living elements into the presence of our urban environment, through processes of mediatization and mediation through art. The main idea is based on the need to reconcile city dwellers with the city, in order to re-enchant local residents with ecological issues through a sensitive approach.

2.1 Hypothesis

Art could make a fundamental contribution to this issue, in this need to share and accept the coexistence of territories [1]. The aim is to reconcile city dwellers with their environment through listening [2], in interactivity with the environment, and to act in favor of an urban and social ecology [3], for better habitability [4]. The idea is to use sound art, aided by web and tangible computer technologies, to affirm our belonging to the living, to raise awareness and encourage citizens to support the principle of co-presence between human and non-human, and to envisage the growth of housing areas in harmony for the future. The medium of music and sound is used in an attempt to translate the potential of a new aesthetic for urban environments, with the idea of anticipating the next practices of the connected city. We postulate that proximity to the territory and to local inhabitants promotes an ecological relationship through tangible interactions and *in situ* devices. We postulate that sound art, thanks to its qualities of social cohesion, mediated by low-tech and high-tech technologies inspired by biomimicry, in a process of sensitive listening, could contribute to strengthening our natural links with living beings and the environment.

2.2 Methodology

The notion of milieu [5] allows us to question the relationships between the environment and its occupants, between the sound

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3.1 Arduino IDE and the web application

To develop this web application³ from an ESP32 Microcontroller board, you can use the Arduino IDE, after configuration, to write the program. It contains two files, an Arduino .ino file and an .h extension file containing the web part. The challenge is to find ways of making the two worlds communicate, so as to be able to use data from the tangible domain and make them compatible with the parameter values of a web audio instrument. Dedicated libraries, declared at the start of the program, are used to instantiate the web part of the application, here #include "htmlCode.h". The Wifi.h and WifiAP.h libraries are used to create the Wi-Fi access point server with fixed IP. The AsyncTCP.h and ESPAsyncWebServer.h libraries are used to create a WebSocket server and manage asynchronous communications between client-server events. The next two libraries are designed for use with sensors. And the last library, Arduino_JSON.h, handles the conversion of data into JSON string format, which is then used to build the application's Javascript objects using the JSONparse() method.

3.2 WebSocket communication

The implementation of a web interface is created from the ESP32 microcontroller using WebSocket technology in a Wi-Fi access point configuration with a fixed IP address (see Figure 3). This enables access to online application content from a local network. All compatible devices can connect to the ESP32 Wi-Fi network without the need for routing. However, the number of connections is limited to eight per card. This is sufficient for small-scale experimentation, while keeping the device deliberately light in order to be as non-invasive as possible and respect the environment as much as possible when interacting with the public. The Wi-Fi access point starts up automatically when the card is powered up, and appears as an open network with no Internet connection requiring, since it's a local network.

```
182 // Handle Web Server
183 server.on("GET", HTTP_GET, [] (AsyncWebServerRequest *request){
184     request->send(200, "text/html", HTML_CONTENT);
185 });
186
187 // Handle Web Server Events
188 events.onConnect([] (AsyncEventSourceClient *client){
189     if(client->lastId()){
190         Serial.printf("Client reconnected! Last message ID that it got is: %u\n", client->lastId());
191     }
192     // send event with message "hello!", id current millis
193     // and set reconnect delay to 1 second
194     client->send("hello!", NULL, millis(), 10000);
195 });
196 server.addHandler(&events);
197
198 server.begin();
199 }
```

Figure 3. WebSocket server on Arduino IDE.

Deep sleep⁴ mode can be programmed to make the device very energy-efficient. The WebSocket server launch protocols are configured to respond to client requests. Once the sensor data is in JSON string format, it is transmitted via events to the web application, in the loop() part via the WebSocket server, to then construct Javascript objects as variables. The millis()⁵ function is

³ <https://github.com/laurentdibiase/Music-for-Elements>

⁴ https://docs.espressif.com/projects/esp-idf/en/stable/esp32/api-reference/system/sleep_modes.html

⁵ <https://docs.arduino.cc/language-reference/en/functions/time/millis/>

a counter for managing time, particularly in the case of multitasking.

3.3 Web Audio and sound synthesis

Variables are then interpreted as sounds in the sound synthesis section created using the Web Audio API. Here, for example (see Figure 4), a small AM synthesis generator is designed to generate a waveform, the frequency and amplitude of which are each modulated by another oscillator. The carrier and modulation variables are chosen as parameters on which a gyro sensor (MPU6050) interacts. In this way, inertial sensor movements modulate the parameters of a sound synthesis algorithm. A link to a demonstration video is available in the footnote⁶.

```
134 // create AM Synth
135 const tremolo = audioContext.createGain();
136 tremolo.gain.value = 0.5;
137 tremolo.connect(audioContext.destination);
138
139 const depth = audioContext.createGain();
140 depth.gain.value = 0.5;
141 depth.connect(tremolo.gain);
142
143 mod = audioContext.createOscillator();
144 mod.frequency.value = defaultModFreq;
145 mod.connect(depth);
146
147 carrier = audioContext.createOscillator();
148 carrier.frequency.value = defaultCarrierFreq;
149 carrier.connect(tremolo);
150
151 carrier.start();
152 mod.start();
153
154 audioContext.onstatechange = function () {
155     console.log(audioContext.state);
156 };
```

Figure 4. Example of Web Audio synthesis generator tested.

4. PROJECT MODEL

A model has been installed on Quai François Mitterrand at the Aubervilliers' lock in Aubervilliers, Seine-Saint-Denis, between Square Aimé Césaire and Quai Lucien Lefranc (see Figure 5). The device invites the public to scan a QR code using their mobile device to connect to the artwork via a local network at each listening point.

Figure 5. Device installed at the listening point *Element 4* with sensors immersed in the canal water.

⁶ <https://vimeo.com/1092844401>

4.1 Artistic and compositional approach

Still in the realization stage, a research project of this kind makes possible the emergence of a form of collaborative composition with the living, where the environment becomes a partner in the process of creating the artwork [8]. In this way, the environment can be approached as a support for composition [9] or as an ambient collaborator [10], capable of what would be on the order of the *musicable* [11] and animated by all the living things that populate it, in the image of ecosystems. Web technologies are strongly linked to the phenomena of mobility, through the use of the Internet and networks. They are therefore, by definition, linked to our perception of geographical territory. And they make it possible to interact in a communicating environment. The use of sound synthesis reinforces the phenomenon of interaction and immersion within a performative and participative condition. However, the composition must take into account the technical condition of listening, through the limited range of the speakers bandwidth built into mobile devices, the number of audience, and at the same time a sort of dialogue between the sound environment and the electronic sound along the walk. For electronic part, a demo sound sample⁷ was made with a synthesizer mobile application, named ModSynth⁸ and created by Brian J. Owings (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Synthesis algorithm used for demo.

4.2 Sonification principles

The sound composition generated by the device is fundamentally linked to the sonification process using techniques such as mapping or interpolation, as well as the threshold technique. The correlation between data values and parameter variables requires the use of communication and possibly conversion tools to ensure consistency between the different layers of the application. For slow signals values, where the variables change very slowly over time, the data is used either as modulation parameters for LFOs and mixing of tracks, or for the use of a continuous drone-type note in the background. All types of slow or fast-changing data can define the oscillator values to define variations in pitch that develop on a scale ratio, and act on the modulation variables of various parameters such as the filters, delays or volumes of amplitude, as well as on the envelope parameters. Slow data allows you to compose patterns in a time frame that is in tune with the rhythm of nature and can interact with any type of parameters.

⁷ <https://soundcloud.com/laurentdibiase/music-for-elements>

⁸ <https://www.brianowings.com/modsynth.html>

5. CONCLUSION

This project also represents an attempt to integrate Web Audio technology in the process of sound co-creation with environmental ecosystems, in conjunction with IoT technologies and the WebSocket API for real-time interaction. The aim is to contribute to current ecological issues and foster links between humans and their environment, in order to re-enchant city dwellers with urban ecology issues. Still in the development phase, results are not yet available, although the technological and artistic processes inspired by biomimicry, DIY design, real-time sound interactions with WebSocket and Web Audio have been validated. Investing in urban green spaces using this ambient device would allow us to question our relationship with living beings and technology through sound art and listening. This project could become an educational tool for recreating ecological links between humans and their environment. This is what we continue to experiment with.

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